

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

INFLUENCE OF QUALITY INDICATORS OF SOIL FERTILITY ON PLANT GROWTH AND DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract

As a result of filtration, when moisture in the soil is replaced by fluids with rheological parameters different from pure water, a full evaluation of the task requires other approaches. It represents both the geometry of the labyrinth system and the non-Newtonian nature of the ground body. Therefore, taking into account the non-Newtonian nature of fluids, in the paper, the calculation dependences of water permeability, initial gradient filtration coefficient, leakage coefficient in connection with rheology have been obtained. The limits of the application of the reporting relationships and the influence of the hydraulic resistance of the soil structure on the irrigation regime are clarified.

Keywords: filtration, water permeability, porosity, water absorption, water conductivity.

The readiness of the soil for the growth and development of agricultural crops is related to special melioration measures.

Among the main defining characteristics of filtration-capillary processes, which correlate with the structure of the soil, the ability to move constituent particles, its potential, it is worth noting water permeability and filtration.

With the change of filtration characteristics, the potential of the soil changes, the prediction of which belongs to the category of tasks that are difficult to solve, and the prediction of fertility is related to differentiated approaches.

As a result of filtration, the change of moisture in the soil is drastically different from that fixed in nature. The fields generated between the particles of different forces participating in the above-mentioned filtration process are conditioned by the law of non-Newtonian resistance of moving water. Consequently, the real model of water movement in the porous system is essentially different from the Newtonian one.

This is confirmed by Darcy's law - the attempts to establish the limits and derive the accounting relationships of the regularity of the real filtration event, to which many scientific works were devoted [1, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12,].

In the soil, which is represented by a highly dispersed system, a characteristic boundary layer with complex properties is formed between the voids of individual particles with energy fields. A general view of it focuses on such a complex of soil property parameters as water permeability and filtration.

Filtration and soil water permeability are related to many interacting factors. During the determination of correlations with their gradient, such a factor as the initial gradient of the shift was identified.

When water moves through the soil through a porous system or interconnected cracks, the task, in such a case, is a part of mechanics, and depending on water permeability, soil fertility depends on its water absorption capacity - chemical, physical-chemical, physical-biological indicators. The water permeability

index is often used as a criterion for differentiating soils from each other.

In a porous system, when the pore radius is equal to the bound water radius, water does not move through the soil and its use by plants is less realistic. When the radius of the bound water is equal to 0, in this case, the plant takes water from the soil smoothly and without any resistance. The determining factor of soil water absorption capacity is the intensity of the acting forces, the axonometry of the porous space, the rheology of the structural space of its body. The filtering parameters and the potential of the abscissas formed on the constituent particles are related to the intensity of the acting forces. In the growth and development of the plant, the influence of the formed link water on the amount of usable productive water and the cost of water used for irrigation is especially important. Depending on the geometry of the pore space, water permeability, filtration, water absorption capacity are related to the volumetric mass and viscosity of the liquid.

Theoretically, the correlation between the initial gradient and the degree of water filling of the pore space can be represented by the model

$$I_0 = a \frac{\varphi}{1 - \varphi} . \quad (1)$$

In the same way, the relationship between the dependence of the filter coefficient of (1) and the initial gradient

$$I_0 = \frac{B}{\sqrt{K}} - 1 . \quad (2)$$

In the (1)-st and (2)-nd dependencies:

I_0 – Initial gradient;

φ – Pore space water filling coefficient;

K – Filtration coefficient (m/sec).

Significance of filtration coefficient based on the combination of the first and second dependencies

$$K = \left(\frac{b}{a} \right)^2 \frac{(1 - \varphi)^2}{\left[1/a^2 - \varphi(1/a - 1) \right]^2} , \quad (3)$$

Though significance of the initial gradient

$$I_0 = \frac{a}{b} \frac{1-\varphi(1-a)}{1-\varphi} \tag{4}$$

When the values of the initial gradient and filtration coefficient in such case are known it makes possible to determine a and b coefficient values, therefore $a = 1$ $B = 1/\varphi$. Based on a.m. according to quality of water filling the porous space the calculation dependences of the initial gradient and the filtration coefficient can be represented by the formulas:

Initial gradient

$$I_0 = \frac{\varphi}{1-\varphi} ; \tag{5}$$

Filtration coefficient

$$K = \frac{(1-\varphi)^2}{\varphi} \tag{6}$$

In order to clarity, the graphical relationship between the filtration coefficient and the degree of water filling of the initial gradient is given in Fig.1.

Fig.1. Graphic dependencies K of filtration coefficient and I_0 initial gradient porous space φ water filling

1. $K = f(\varphi)$ and 2. $I_0 = f(\varphi)$

It is known that in case of viscous mixture with existence of multiple particles theoretically the viscosity is defined by linear dependencies.

$$\mu = \mu_0(1 + 2,5\varphi) , \tag{7}$$

Where μ , μ_0 – are values of disperse system and environment viscosity, Pa·s;

φ – volume concentration.

If we evaluate time of movement of Non-Newtonian viscous fluid in a pipe and the pressure value by Darcy-Weerbach model, when the length of a pipe - ℓ -, radius R , heaviness power acceleration - g and hydraulic resistance coefficient is λ .

$$h = \lambda \frac{\ell}{4R} \frac{U^2}{2g} . \tag{8}$$

Based on simplification and transformation of (8) dependence, when in a pipe with R radius the water movement is evaluated with Reinold valuer Re_r – and pressure gradient value

$$I = \lambda \frac{R_{Re}^2 v^2}{R^2} \frac{1}{8gR} . \tag{9}$$

In – (9) accounting dependence when the coefficient of hydraulic resistance $\lambda = A/R_{Re}^{2-n}$ and value of pressure loss

$$I = \frac{AR_{Re}^n}{8} \frac{v^2}{gR^3} . \tag{10}$$

Number of Π filtration, when I s is represented by unmeasurable value and is equal to $\Pi = AR_{Re}^n / 8$, at the same time the average speed of movement of quality index $\Pi = 1$,

$$U = \frac{\gamma}{\mu} KI . \tag{11}$$

Accrdingly the filtration rate in the soil-ground may be defined since the rate of filtration in the soil-ground pipe is equal to average rate multiplied by m porosity $V_{por} = Um$

$$V_{por} = \frac{\gamma}{\mu} K' m l . \quad (12)$$

In case of linear water permeability, the value of the coefficient of water permeability is represented by the formula

$$K_0 = K' m , \quad (13)$$

The value of the filtration coefficient

$$K = K_0 \frac{\gamma}{\mu} . \quad (14)$$

Filtration speed

$$V = \frac{\gamma}{\mu} K_0 I . \quad (15)$$

When Non-Newtonian fluid moves in a pipe, the value of average speed

$$V^H = \frac{\gamma R^2}{3\mu} \Psi^2 \left[1 - \sqrt{1 - m(1,5 - 0,5\sqrt{1 - m})} \right] \quad (16)$$

Where γ – the volume mass (kg/m³);

μ – the viscosity coefficient is (kg.sec/m²);

Ψ – the coefficient of inner friction is;

m – the link is the ratio of the water radius to the pipe radius.

If we multiply both sides of the equation (16) by the porosity and consider the received value as the filtration rate, we have

$$V^H \cdot m = \frac{\gamma R^2}{3\mu} m \Psi^2 \left[1 - \sqrt{1 - m(1,5 - 0,5\sqrt{1 - m})} \right] \quad (17)$$

since $\frac{\gamma R^2}{3\mu}$ represents the average rate of Newtonian fluid in a pipe, the connection between filtration rate of Newtonian and Non-Newtonian fluids

$$V_{por}^H = V_{por} \Psi^2 \left[1 - \sqrt{1 - m(1,5 - 0,5\sqrt{1 - m})} \right] \quad (18)$$

In case of linear filtration, considering initial

gradient $I \left(1 - \frac{I_0}{I} \right)$ and $f(\beta)$,

$$f(\beta) = \Psi^2 \left[1 - \sqrt{1 - m(1,5 - 0,5\sqrt{1 - m})} \right]$$

filtration rate

$$V_{por}^H = \frac{\gamma}{\mu} K_0 I f(\beta) \left(1 - \frac{I_0}{I} \right) . \quad (19)$$

Filtration coefficient to-(19) dependency

$$K = \frac{\gamma}{\mu} K_0 I f(\beta) \left(1 - \frac{I_0}{I} \right) \quad (20)$$

If in-(20) dependency we imagine filtration in relation with characteristics, that is $K^H = \gamma^H K_0^H / \mu^H$, the value of filtration rate

$$V_{por}^H = \frac{\gamma^H}{\mu^H} K_0^H I_0^H . \quad (21)$$

Taking into account (21), in-(20)-the value of the permeability coefficient is

$$K_0^H = K_0 \frac{\gamma}{\gamma^H} \frac{\mu^H}{\mu} \frac{I}{I^n} \left(1 - \frac{I_0}{I} \right) f(\beta) \quad (22)$$

In case of linear filtration, when the filtration rate

$$V_{por}^H = K^H I^H \text{ and } I = I^n$$

$$K^H I^H = K_0 I \left(1 - \frac{I_0}{I} \right) f(\beta) , \quad (23)$$

Thus dependence between filtration coefficients is

$$\frac{K^H}{K} = \left(1 - \frac{I_0}{I} \right) f(\beta) . \quad (24)$$

Many experiments have been devoted to the study of the relationship between the Reynolds number and hydraulic resistance. Ch. is especially noteworthy. Studies conducted by Slichter, on the basis of which the critical value of the Reynolds number during the change of hydraulic resistance is placed in the limits $7.5 \leq R_{Re} \leq 9.0$ [2].

If we equate the calculated dependence of soil-ground water permeability with the product of the pipeline area with the porosity, when the radius of the pipeline is equal to R

$$K' m = \pi R^2 \left(1 - \frac{r_0}{R} \right)^2 m \quad (25)$$

Thus

$$\frac{8}{A \left(1 - \frac{r_0}{R} \right)^2} = \pi \quad (26)$$

The Hydraulic resistance coefficient is

$$\lambda = \frac{2,5 R_{Re}}{(1 - m)^2} \quad (27)$$

While $\lambda = \frac{64}{R_{Re}}$ and is considered laminar

movement the amount of bound water surrounding the soil particles $r_0 = 0,8R$ (28)

Based on Slichter's results, the relationship between the coefficient of hydraulic resistance and the degree of waterlogging of the soil is given by a graphical relationship $\lambda = f(R_{Re}, m)$

Fig.2. Relation of hydraulic resistance to porosity at different values of Reynolds number

1. $R_{Re} = 7.5$; 2. $R_{Re} = 8.0$; 3. $R_{Re} = 9.0$.

When irrigating the area with irrigation water of increased concentration, the value of the pressure gradient changes from the maximum value to a value close to one at the end of irrigation. Along with this, the rate of water absorption decreases to a constant value.

Along with this, due to contact of soil with water, its mechanical and physico-chemical characteristics change, the structure of the soil is broken-densified, water permeability decreases, etc.

The phenomenon of water absorption in the soil is particularly influenced by the capillary forces of air and water in the pores.

If we use as an analogue the infiltration of water into the soil at d depth to the change in the dynamics of water permeability or water absorption rate, the rate of water absorption can be determined

$$U_t^H = U_t f(\beta) I_t \left(1 - \frac{I_0}{I_t}\right) = \frac{K_1}{t^\alpha} \left(1 - \frac{I_0}{I_t}\right) f(\beta) \quad (28)$$

Where U_t - the rate of water absorption t on the moment of time (m/sec);

K_t - Water permeability coefficient in the ground-soil t in a moment;

I_t - pressure coefficient;

K_1 - Water permeability coefficient at a first moment of time;

α - The quality indicator changes depending on the soil composition and humidity $0,3 \div 0,80$;

The value of the fluid filtration coefficient in the ground in a moment of time T in relation of time

$$K_1^H = K_1 \left(1 - \frac{I_0}{I_t}\right) f(\beta) T^\alpha \quad (30)$$

t - average value of permeability in a time

$$K_{ar.}^H = \frac{1}{t} \int_0^t \frac{K_t (1 - I_0 / I_t) f(\beta)}{t^\alpha} dt = \frac{K_0 (1 - I_0 / I_t) f(\beta)}{t^\alpha} \quad (31)$$

The filtration coefficient, by which the water permeability of the soil is characterized, relates to the magnitude of grooving of its body. It is an indicator of soil structure as a function of diameter, volumetric mass and

viscosity and plays a special role in moisture regulation.

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